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Infodemic during COVID-19 Outbreak: the Role of Library Professionals

Subhajit Panda

Assistant Librarian, Chandigarh University, Mohali, Punjab (India)

Email: subhajit.e9641@cumail.in

Abstract:

During the COVID-19 pandemic situation, when information outbreak is enormous, it is the time to remind the society of the importance of libraries and librarians in organising and disseminating accurate & reliable information. Accurate information is the key to handling a chaotic situation. The exchange of false information seems to be on the rise. It has created a situation of 'infodemic' as stated by the Director-General of the World Health Organization (WHO). This has not only affected research work severely but has also created chaos among the laypeople. The present study tries to investigate the attitude, perception & responsibility of a library professional for this purpose as they are the essential provider of information for academic as well as a social community. The study was carried through a short online survey with a structured questionnaire designed on a Google form. A total of 150 respondents (N) was selected for the study over four designated domains viz. Library Assistant, Assistant Librarian, Deputy Librarian and University Librarian. The findings of the study reveal that some part of regular citizen, political leaders, attention seekers & profiteers, and heavily partisan news media are the top responsible sources of infodemic; while WhatsApp & Facebook takes the lead as a major platform for this purpose. Additionally, the study throws light on harms done to people due to this infodemic e.g. anxiety, insomnia, depression and negative thoughts. As an essential practice to fight against such infodemic, all types of library professionals agree to crosscheck information from authentic sources before sharing with others but also take into account updating yourself from time to time with sufficient information as well as not trusting blindly on everything over the internet. Again, the majority of the library professionals agreed with more than one way to stop such infodemic situation, which includes conducting information literacy programmes, social talk, surveys & webinars to ensure mental richness of the user, spreading awareness about official and fake websites, training common people about how to identify & report misinformation etc.

Keywords: Infodemic, COVID-19, Library Professionals, India, Social Media, Misinformation, Physical Problems, Psychological Issues

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**Presented By
Mr.Subhajit Panda
Assistant Librarian, University Library, Chandigarh University**

INFORMATION, MISINFORMATION & DISINFORMATION

INFORMATION

- **Information is what we call things that are accurate to the best of our current knowledge.** For instance, COVID-19 stands for coronavirus disease 2019 and is caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. One of the difficulties with any new pathogen, like this coronavirus, is that information changes over time as we learn more about the science.

MISINFORMATION

- Misinformation, on the other hand, is false information. Importantly, **it is false information that was not created with the intention of hurting others.** Misinformation is often started by someone who genuinely wants to understand a topic and cares about keeping other people safe and well. It is then shared by others who feel the same. Everyone believes they are sharing good information – but unfortunately, they are not. And depending on what is being shared, the misinformation can turn out to be quite harmful.

Misinformation is incorrect or misleading information.

It's not created with the intention of hurting others.

DISINFORMATION

- At the other end of the spectrum is disinformation. **Unlike misinformation, this is false information created with the intention of profiting from it or causing harm.** That harm could be to a person, a group of people, an organization or even a country. Disinformation generally serves some agenda and can be dangerous. During this pandemic, we are seeing it used to try to erode our trust in each other and in our government and public institutions.

Disinformation is deliberate misinformation. It's designed to deceive or mislead.

MISINFORMATION Vs. DISINFORMATION

Misinformation can be an innocent mistake, but it's still dangerous.

Disinformation is dangerous, plus it serves someone else's agenda.

INFODEMIC

- Infodemic refers to *a large increase in the volume of information associated with a specific topic* and whose growth can occur exponentially in a short period of time due to a specific incident, such as the current pandemic COVID-19.
- As stated by the WHO, the COVID-19 outbreak and response has been accompanied by *a massive infodemic: an overabundance of information – some accurate and some not – that makes it hard for people to find trustworthy sources and reliable guidance when they need it.*
- In this situation, misinformation and rumors appear on the scene, along with manipulation of information with doubtful intent. In the information age, this phenomenon is amplified through social networks, spreading further and faster like a virus.

Contribution of Infodemic in Spreading Misinformation

- Increased global access to cell phones with an Internet connection, as well as social media, has led to the exponential production of information and the number of possible paths for getting it, creating an **information epidemic or infodemic**. In other words, we have a situation where a lot of information is being produced and shared to every corner of the world, reaching billions of people. How much of this information is accurate? Just some of it
- **It is key to break this dangerous cycle:** misinformation expands at the same pace as content production and distribution paths grow. So the very same infodemic accelerates and perpetuates misinformation
- **Access to the right information, at the right time, in the right format IS CRITICAL!**

SPREADING OF MISINFORMATION

Information spreads like a virus.

So does misinformation and disinformation. When it's exciting, it can spread even faster.

And that can be deadly.

So we need to critically assess information before we share it.

SPREADING & AVOIDING MISINFORMATION

- **We are all being exposed to a huge amount of COVID-19 information on a daily basis, and not all of it is reliable. Here are some tips for telling the difference and stopping the spread of misinformation.**

TOP TIPS TO NAVIGATING THE INFODEMIC

Top tips for navigating the infodemic

1. Assess the source:

Who shared the information with you and where did they get it from? Even if it is friends or family, you still need to vet their source.

2. Go beyond headlines:

Headlines may be intentionally sensational or provocative.

3. Identify the author:

Search the author's name online to see if they are real or credible.

4. Check the date:

Is it up to date and relevant to current events? Has a headline, image or statistic been used out of context?

5. Examine the supporting evidence:

Credible stories back up their claims with facts.

6. Check your biases:

Think about whether your own biases could affect your judgment on what is or is not trustworthy.

7. Turn to fact-checkers:

Consult trusted fact-checking organizations, such as the International Fact-Checking Network and global news outlets focused on debunking misinformation.

WHO: INFODEMIC

“‘We’re not just fighting an epidemic; we’re fighting an infodemic’...”

- Aleksandra Kuzmanovic, Social Media Manager, WHO (Department of Communications)

- She Further stated,
 - “fighting infodemics and misinformation is a joint effort between our technical risk communications [team] and colleagues who are working on the EPI-WIN platform, where they communicate with different...professionals providing them with advice and guidelines and also receiving information”
(EPI-WIN: WHO Information Network for Epidemics)
 - “...I am in touch with Facebook, Twitter, Tencent, Pinterest, TikTok, and also my colleagues in the China office who are working closely with Chinese social media platforms...So when we see some questions or rumours spreading, we write it down, we go back to our risk communications colleagues and then they help us find evidence-based answers”.

WHO: INFODEMIC

- Another thing we are doing with social media platforms, and that is something we are putting our strongest efforts in, is to ensure no matter where people live....when they're on Facebook, Twitter, or Google, when they search for 'coronavirus' or 'COVID-19' or [a] related term, they have a box that...directs them to a reliable source: either to [the] WHO website to their ministry of health or public health institute or centre for disease control”

The COVID-19 social media infodemic

Upper panel: activity (likes, comments, reposts, etc.) distribution for each social media. Middle panel: most discussed topics about COVID-19 on each social media. Lower panel: cumulative number of content (posts, tweets, videos, etc.) produced from the 1st of January to the 14th of February. Due to the Twitter API limitations in gathering past data, the first data point for Twitter is dated January 27th. (Cinelli et al, 2020)

How Infodemic Make this Pandemic Worse?

- **Makes it hard for people**, decision makers, and health workers to find trustworthy sources and reliable guidance when they need it. Sources may be apps, scientific organizations, websites, blogs, “influencers,” and more
- **People may feel anxiety**, depression, overwhelmed, emotionally drained, and unable to meet important demands
- **It can affect decision-making processes** when immediate answers are expected and not enough time is allotted to deeply analyze the evidence
- **No quality control** on what’s published, and sometimes, on what’s used to take action and make decisions
- **Anybody can write or publish anything on the web** (podcasts, articles, etc.), in particular on social media channels (individual and institutional accounts)

THE SURVEY

Target Sample Group: Library Professionals

Survey Medium: Online

Questionnaire Platform: Google form

No of Question: 10

Survey Date: 28 November - 12 December, 2020

No of Responses: 183

Selected Sample Size : 150

Research Sample Size & Category

Total Respondant = 150

Gender Wise

Total Respondant = 150

Designation Wise

Comparative Percentage of Social Media Activeness

Frequency of Encountering Misinformation on Social Media

Top Cited Sources of Misinformation by the Respondents (in %)

Top Cited Social Platforms for Spreading Misinformation (in %)

Our Fault & Contribution of Spreading Misinformation (in %)

Most Harmful Effect due to Spreading of Misinformation (in %)

Practices to be Adopted to Fight Against COVID-19 Misinformation (in %)

Responsibility of a Library Professional to Stop Spreading Misinformation (in %)

CONCLUSION

- Thus, it is evident from the present study that social media has undoubtedly revolutionized modern-day easy communication system, at the same time, it has also brought with it new problems. Unmoderated, easy to use, free & highly population rich social is currently believed to be the main sources of misinformation on COVID-19. The platforms of every social media now accompanied by a large amount of misleading and false information that directly give a negative influence on the widespread adoption of health-protective behaviours in the population. Scientists and other information specialists already work proactively to solve this issue and provide common people correct information about the pandemic. There is an urgent need for highly skilled scholars to assume a greater role in moderating information flow on COVID-19 via established and emerging platforms for scholarly communication. And in this area library professional, as an information moderator (in the right way to the right person & in the right time) can contribute his best to stop misinformation from spreading over social media. The findings of the present study will help the public, in general, to be cautious about misinformation, and the respective authority of a country, in particular, for initiating proper safety measures about disastrous misinformation to protect the public health from being exploited.

Thank you

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